

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEDIPASVIR AND
SOFOSBUVIR IN PURE AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE
FORM BY USING RP-HPLC****Nagula Nikitha *, Dr. G. Vijay Kumar**Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, KGR Institute Of Technology And Management
Rampally, Secunderabad, Telangana-501301**Abstract:**

The analytical method was developed by studying different parameters. First of all, maximum absorbance was found to be at 240 nm and the peak purity was excellent. Injection volume was selected to be 10 μ l which gave a good peak area. The column used for study was Phenomenex Gemini C₁₈ because it was giving good peak. 40°C temperature was found to be suitable for the nature of drug solution. The flow rate was fixed at 1.0ml/min because of good peak area and satisfactory retention time. Mobile phase is Methanol: Water (75:25% v/v) was fixed due to good symmetrical peak. So this mobile phase was used for the proposed study. Run time was selected to be 10 min because analyze gave peak around 2.256, 5.427 $\pm$ 0.02min respectively and also to reduce the total run time. The percent recovery was found to be 98.0-102 was linear and precise over the same range. Both system and method precision was found to be accurate and well within range. The analytical method was found linearity over the range 5-25mg/ml of Ledipasavir and 25- 125 mg/ml of Sofosbavir of the target concentration. The analytical passed both robustness and ruggedness tests. On both cases, relative standard deviation was well satisfactory.

Corresponding author:**Nagula Nikitha ***Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
KGR Institute of Technology and Management Rampally,
Secunderabad, Telangana.
Email Id- nagulanikitha@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nagula Nikitha et al., *Analytical Method Development And Validation For Simultaneous Estimation Of Ledipasvir And Sofosbuvir In Pure And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form By Using Rp-Hplc.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).

1. INTRODUCTION:

Importance of drug analysis

'Health is wealth'. It is vital fact that a healthy body is desire of every human being. Good health is first condition to enjoy the life and all other things which mankind is having. Nowadays peoples are more concentrating towards health. Even governmental bodies of different countries and World health organization (WHO) are also focusing for health of human being. Health care is prevention, treatment and management of illness and preservation of mental and physical well being. Health care embraces all the goods and services designed to promote health including preventive, curative and palliative in interventions. The Health care industry is considered an industry or profession which includes people's exercise of skill or judgment or providing of a service related to the prevention or improvement of the health of the individuals or the treatment or care of individuals who are injured, sick, disabled or infirm. The delivery of modern health care depends on an Interdisciplinary Team.

The medical model of health focuses on the eradication of illness through diagnosis and effective treatment. A traditional view is that improvement in health results from advancements in medical science. Advancements in medical science bring varieties of medicines. Medicines are key part of the health care system. The numerous medicines are introducing into the world- market and also, that is increasing every year. These medicines are being either new entities or partial structural modification of the existing one. So, to evaluate quality and efficacy of these medicines is also important factor. Right from the beginning of discovery of any medicine quality and efficacy of the same are checked by quantification means. Quality and efficacy are checked by either observing effect of drug on various animal models or analytical means. The option of animal models is not practically suitable for every batch of medicine as it's require long time, high cost and more man-power. Later option of analytical way is more suitable, highly precise, safe and selective.

The analytical way deals with quality standards which are assigned for products to have desirable efficacy of the medicines. Sample representing any batch are analyzed for these standards and it is assumed that drug/medicine which is having such standards are having desire effect on use. Quality control is a concept, which strives to produce a perfect product by series of measures designed to prevent and eliminate

errors at different stage of production. The decision to release or reject a product is based on one or more type of control action.

Due to rapid growth of pharmaceutical industry during last several years, number of pharmaceutical formulations are enter as a part of health care system and thus, there has been rapid progress in the field of pharmaceutical analysis. Developing analytical method for newly introduced pharmaceutical formulation is a matter of most importance because drug or drug combination may not be official in any pharmacopoeias and thus, no analytical method for quantification is available. To check the quality standards of the medicine various analytical methods are used. Modern analytical techniques are playing key role in assessing chemical quality standards of medicine. Thus analytical techniques are required for fixing standards of medicines and its regular checking. Out of all analytical techniques, the technique which is widely used to check the quality of drug is known as 'CHROMATOGRAPHY'.

History of chromatography and HPLC

In 1903 a Russian botanist Mikhail Tswett produced a colorful separation of plant pigments through calcium carbonate column. Chromatography word came from Greek language chroma = color and graphein = to write i.e. color writing or chromatography[1, 2]. Prior to the 1970's, few reliable chromatographic methods were commercially available to the laboratory scientist. During 1970's, most chemical separations were carried out using a variety of techniques including open-column chromatography, paper chromatography, and thin-layer chromatography. However, these chromatographic techniques were inadequate for quantification of compounds and resolution between similar compounds. During this time, pressure liquid chromatography began to be used to decrease flow through time, thus reducing purification times of compounds being isolated by column chromatography. However, flow rates were inconsistent, and the question of whether it was better to have constant flow rate or constant pressure was debated[3]. High pressure liquid chromatography was developed in the mid-1970's and quickly improved with the development of column packing materials and the additional convenience of on-line detectors. In the late 1970's, new methods including reverse phase liquid chromatography allowed for improved separation between very similar compounds. By the 1980's HPLC was

commonly used for the separation of chemical compounds. New techniques improved separation, identification, purification and quantification far above the previous techniques. Computers and automation added to the convenience of HPLC. Improvements in type of columns and thus reproducibility were made as such terms as micro-column, affinity columns, and Fast HPLC began to immerge.

By the 2000 very fast development was undertaken in the area of column material with small particle size technology and other specialized columns. The dimensions of the General Introduction typical HPLC column are 100-300 mm in length with an internal diameter between 3-5 mm. The usual diameter of micro-columns, or capillary columns, ranges from 3 μm to 200 μm [4]. In this decade sub 2 micron particle size technology (column material packed with silica particles of $2\mu\text{m}$ size) with modified or improved HPLC instrumentation becomes a popular with different instrument brand name like UPLC (Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography) of Waters and RRLC (Rapid Resolution Liquid Chromatography) of Agilent.

Types of Chromatography

The mobile phase could be either a liquid or a gas, and accordingly we can subdivide chromatography into Liquid Chromatography (LC) or Gas Chromatography (GC). Apart from these methods, there are two other modes that use a liquid mobile phase, but the nature of its transport through the porous stationary phase is in the form of either (a) capillary forces, as in planar chromatography (also called Thin-Layer Chromatography, TLC), or (b) electro osmotic flow, as in the case of Capillary Electro Chromatography (CEC).

MATERIALS AND METHODS: INSTRUMENTS USED

HPLC from WATERS, software: Empower 2, Alliance 2695 separation module. 996 PDA detector.

CHEMICALS USED:

Sofosbuvir and Ledipasvir from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK) and Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

TRAILS

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Sofosbuvir and Ledipasvir working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol. Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Sofosbuvir and 0.3ml of the Ledipasvir stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

VALIDATION

PREPARATION OF BUFFER AND MOBILE PHASE:

Preparation of Potassium dihydrogen Phosphate (KH₂PO₄) buffer (pH-4.6):

Dissolve 6.8043 of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml HPLC water and adjust the pH 4.6 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Filter and sonicate the solution by vacuum filtration and ultra sonication.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 450 ml (45%) of Methanol, 550 ml of Phosphate buffer (55%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultrasonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimize d Chromatogram
Table: - peak results for optimized

S. No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Ledipasavir	2.256	84995	13906	---	1.33	5536
2	Sofosbavir	5.427	377907	39949	16.28	1.04	9102

Observation: From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Ledipasavir and Sofosbavir peaks are well separated and they shows proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So it's optimized trial.

Figure: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Table: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

S. No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Ledipasavir	2.246	86053	33062		1.33	5507
2	Sofosbavir	5.461	364679	39374	16.43	1.01	9148

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

VALIDATION**Blank:**

Fig: Chromatogram showing blank (mobile phase preparation)

System suitability:**Results of system suitability for Ledipasavir**

S no	Name	R _t	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Ledipasavir	2.247	86093	14052	5507	1.36
2	Ledipasavir	2.246	85627	14026	5675	1.2
3	Ledipasavir	2.248	85558	14133	5299	1.2
4	Ledipasavir	2.252	86142	14307	5033	1.0
5	Ledipasavir	2.248	86558	14153	5811	1.33
Mean			85995.6			
Std. Dev			410.662			
% RSD			0.477538			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table: Results of system suitability for Sofosbavir

S no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Sofosbavir	5.452	376066	39374	9147	1.04	15.0
2	Sofosbavir	5.484	373326	39428	9025	1.5	15.5
3	Sofosbavir	5.491	373434	39404	9166	1.2	15.3
4	Sofosbavir	5.482	375114	39746	9077	1.1	15.1
5	Sofosbavir	5.491	373436	39404	9328	1.2	15.2
Mean			374275.2				
Std. Dev			1247.338				
% RSD			0.333268				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

SPECIFICITY

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components.

Analytical method was tested for specificity to measure accurately quantitate Ledipasavir and Sofosbavir in drug product.

Assay (Standard):**Table: Peak results for assay standard**

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Ledipasavir	2.256	84995	13906		1.31	3536
2	Sofosbavir	5.427	377907	39949	16.28	1.04	9102
3	Ledipasavir	2.249	86395	14164		1.37	3702
4	Sofosbavir	5.430	376778	39936	16.14	1.06	9361
5	Ledipasavir	2.248	85871	14083		1.41	3685
6	Sofosbavir	5.443	375761	39608	16.18	1.06	9229

Assay (Sample):

Table: Peak results for Assay sample

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Ledipasavir	2.247	86093	36066		1.36	9507	1
2	Sofosbavir	5.452	376778	37985	16.43	1.38	9512	1
3	Ledipasavir	2.246	86053	33062		1.32	9488	2
4	Sofosbavir	5.461	364678	39374	16.41	1.04	9147	2
5	Ledipasavir	2.243	84183	39538		1.03	9229	3
6	Sofosbavir	5.466	385424	39458	16.49	1.02	9248	3

$$\% \text{ASSAY} = \frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{table}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{\text{Weight of}} \times 100$$

Standard area Dilution of standard Weight of sample 100 Label claim
 The % purity of Ledipasavir and Sofosbavir in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.4 %.

LINEARITY

CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY:

Ledipasavir:

Concentration Level (%)	Concentration □g/ml	Average Peak Area
33.3	5	51081
66.6	10	92209
100	15	139141
2133.3	20	180999
166.6	25	223921

Figure 6.3.4 calibration graph for Ledipasavir

CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY:**Ledipasavir:**

Concentration Level (%)	Concentration μ g/ml	Average Peak Area
33.3	5	51081
66.6	10	92209
100	15	139141
2133.3	20	180999
166.6	25	223921

Figure 6.3.4 calibration graph for Ledipasavir**LINEARITY PLOT:**

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Ledipasavir is a straight line.

$Y = mx + c$ Slope (m) = 8893

Intercept (c) = 3394

Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.999

SOFOBSAVIRIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 3394.

Sofosbavir

Concentration Level (%)	Concentration $\square$ g/ml	Average Peak Area
33	25	224574
66	50	441896
100	75	635378
133	100	842227
166	125	1041382

Figure 6.3.4 calibration graph for Sofosbavir**LINEARITY PLOT:**

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Sofosbavir is a straight line.

$Y = mx + c$ Slope (m) = 8289

Intercept (c) = 12813

Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.999

SOFOSBAVIRIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 12813.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

REPEATABILITY

Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Fig. Chromatogram showing precision injection -5 Table: Results of repeatability for Ledipasavir

S no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Ledipasavir	2.269	85149	13803	3406.7	1.4
2	Ledipasavir	2.255	85368	13827	3338.4	1.4
3	Ledipasavir	2.252	85452	13798	3475.5	1.4
4	Ledipasavir	2.267	85813	13859	3423.2	1.4
5	Ledipasavir	2.260	87008	14017	3327.6	1.3
<u>Mean</u>		2.264	87210	13985	3417.4	1.4
<u>Std. Dev</u>			85998.6			
<u>% RSD</u>			881.5			
			1.1			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table: Results of method precession for Sofosbavir:

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Sofosbavir	5.274	370077	40628	9076.5	1.1	15.4
2	Sofosbavir	5.266	370127	40936	9121.4	1.1	15.6
3	Sofosbavir	5.265	372485	41278	9213.4	1.1	15.3
4	Sofosbavir	5.278	376525	41455	8884.0	1.1	15.3
5	Sofosbavir	5.305	381813	41321	9042.5	1.1	15.3
Mean		5.319	374205.4	41134	8975.1	1.1	15.3
Std. Dev			4997.323				
% RSD			1.335449				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Intermediate precision:**Day 1:****Results of Intermediate precision for Ledipasavir**

S no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Ledipasavir	2.248	84028	13604	3518.3	1.4
2	Ledipasavir	2.245	84203	13521	3373.9	1.4
3	Ledipasavir	2.242	84746	13637	3412.8	1.4
4	Ledipasavir	2.239	85443	13776	3324.5	1.3
5	Ledipasavir	2.243	85536	13769	3434.4	1.4
6	Ledipasavir	2.246	85698	13738	3337.9	1.3
Mean			84942			
Std. Dev			720.3716			
% RSD			0.8			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table: Results of Intermediate precision for Sofosbavir

S no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Sofosbavir	5.284	366832	40103	9181.2	1.1	15.8
2	Sofosbavir	5.293	368857	40465	9156.6	1.1	15.5
3	Sofosbavir	5.306	370175	39978	9038.6	1.0	15.5
4	Sofosbavir	5.319	370604	40749	9118.3	1.1	15.8
5	Sofosbavir	5.346	372579	39773	9184.9	1.1	15.6
6	Sofosbavir	5.352	376551	40084	9008.1	1.1	15.9
Mean			370933				
Std. Dev			3349.08				
% RSD			0.9				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

Table: Results of Intermediate precision for Sofosbavir

S no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Sofosbavir	5.266	368857	39978	9038.6	1.0	15.5
2	Sofosbavir	5.265	370175	40749	9118.3	1.1	15.8
3	Sofosbavir	5.306	370604	39773	9184.9	1.1	15.6
4	Sofosbavir	5.293	369543	40084	9008.1	1.1	15.9
5	Sofosbavir	5.265	371266	56431	9024.8	1.2	15.1
6	Sofosbavir	5.266	378532	47653	9124.1	1.0	15.3
Mean			371496.2				
Std. Dev			3546.194				
% RSD			0.9				

The accuracy results for Sofosbavir

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	322955	37.6	38.4	98.7	99.8%
100%	632156	76	75.7	99.7	
150%	945871.3	113.5	113.5	101	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact Sofosbavir.

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result:**Ledipasvir:**

$$= 3.3 \times 1476.576536 / 8893$$

$$= 0.54 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

Sofosbuvir:

$$= 3.3 \times 6116.701941 / 8289$$

$$= 2.4 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

LIMIT OF QUANTITATION

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined.

$$LOQ = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response S = Slope of the calibration curve **Result:**

Ledipasvir:

$$= 10 \times 1476.576536 / 8893$$

= 1.6 μ g/ml

Sofosbavir:

= $10 \times 6116.701941/8289$

= 7.3 μ g/ml

Robustness

The robustness was performed for the flow rate variations from 0.9 ml/min to 1.1 ml/min and mobile phase ratio variation from more organic phase to less organic phase ratio for Ledipasavir and Sofosbavir. The method is robust only in less flow condition and the method is robust even by change in the Mobile phase $\pm 5\%$. The standard and samples of Ledipasavir and Sofosbavir were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

Variation in flow

Figure: chromatogram showing less flow of 0.9ml/min

Figure: chromatogram showing more flow of 1.1 ml/min

Variation of mobile phase organic composition

Figure: chromatogram showing less organic composition

Figure: chromatogram showing more organic composition

Table: Results for Robustness Ledipasavir:

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	84995	2.256	5536	1.31
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	89988	2.505	5892	1.28
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	80654	2.046	5084	1.21
Less organic phase	89988	2.505	5099	1.22
More organic phase	80655	2.046	5124	1.29

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Sofosbavir:

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	377907	5.427	9102	1.01
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	397681	5.599	9408	1.03
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	327898	4.576	9585	0.98
Less organic phase	396751	5.599	9406	1.02
More organic phase	339026	4.576	9585	0.99

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY

The analytical method was developed by studying different parameters.

First of all, maximum absorbance was found to be at 240 nm and the peak purity was excellent. Injection volume was selected to be 10 μ l which gave a good peak area.

The column used for study was Phenomenex Gemini C₁₈ because it was giving good peak.

40°C temperature was found to be suitable for the nature of drug solution. The flow rate was fixed at 1.0ml/min because of good peak area and satisfactory retention time.

Mobile phase is Methanol: Water (75:25% v/v) was fixed due to good symmetrical peak. So this mobile phase was used for the proposed study.

Run time was selected to be 10 min because analyze gave peak around 2.256, 5.427 $\pm$ 0.02min respectively and also to reduce the total run time.

The percent recovery was found to be 98.0-102 was linear and precise over the same range. Both system and method precision was found to be accurate and well within range.

The analytical method was found linearity over the range 5-25mg/ml of Ledipasavir and 25- 125 mg/ml of Sofosbavir of the target concentration.

The analytical passed both robustness and ruggedness tests. On both cases, relative standard deviation was well satisfactory.

REFERENCES:

1. Meyer V.R. Practical High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, 4th Ed. England, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, (2004), PP 7-8.
2. Sahajwalla CG a new drug development, vol 141, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, (2004), PP 421–426.
3. Introduction to Column. (Online), URL: http://amitpatel745.topcities.com/index_files/study/column_care.pdf
4. Detectors used in HPLC (online)URL: http://wiki.answers.com/Q/What_detectors_are_used_in_HPLC
5. Detectors (online) ,URL: http://hplc.chem.shu.edu/NEW/HPLC_Book/Detectors/det_uvda.html
6. <http://www.umich.edu/~orgolab/Chroma/chromahis.html>
7. From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia
8. <http://kerouac.pharm.uky.edu/asrg/hplc/history.html>
9. http://www.laballiance.com/la_info%5Csupport%5Chplc3.htm
10. Vander Wal S, Snyder LR. J. Chromatogr. 225 (1983) 463.
11. A Practical Guide to HPLC Detection, Academic Press, San Diego, CA, (1983).
12. Poole CF, Schutte SA. Contemporary Practice of Chromatography, Elsevier, Amsterdam, (1984) 375.
13. Krull IS. In Chromatography and Separation Chemistry: Advances and Developments,

- Ahuja S. ed., ACS Symposium Series 297, ACS, Washington, DC, (1986) 137.
14. Li G, Szulc ME, Fischer DH, Krull IS. In Electrochemical Detection in Liquid Chromatography and Capillary Electrophoresis, Kissinger PT. edn., Chromatography Science Series, Marcel Dekker, New York, (1997).
 15. Kissinger PT, Heineman WR. eds., Laboratory Techniques in Electroanalytical Chemistry, Chapter 20, Marcel Dekker, New York, (1984).
 17. Swarbrick JC, Boylan James, Encyclopedia of pharmaceutical technology, Vol. I (1998) 217-224.
 18. Lindsay Sandy, HPLC by open learning, (1991) 30-45.
 19. Lough WJ, Wainer IWW. HPLC fundamental principles and practices, (1991) 52-67.
 20. Dr.Kealey and P.J.Haines, Analytical Chemistry, 1stedition, Bios Publisher,(2002),PP:1-7.